

suspension of Raney nickel (W-2 ; 27.0 g) in ethanol (100.0 ml) and the resulting mixture was refluxed with constant stirring for 150 min. The used-up Raney nickel was removed by hot filtration. The solvent was distilled out from the filtrate, and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to yield the product (2a) (3.4 g, 80%), m.p. 150° (Found : N, 19.65. Req'd. for $C_{13}H_{13}N_3$: N, 19.90%); ν_{max} 3 375 (NH), 1 635 (C=N), 1 372 (Ar), 1 295 (C-N) and 1 070 cm^{-1} (Ar -Cl)⁷⁻⁹; δ 7.05-7.40 (ArH); 2a afforded a hydrochloride when treated with concentrated hydrochloric acid, m.p. 138° (Found : Eq. wt., 240.8. Req'd. for $C_{13}H_{13}N_3 \cdot HCl$: Eq. wt., 247.5); its ethanolic solution when mixed with aqueous picric acid gave a picrate, m.p. 170° (Found : N, 19.39. Req'd. for $C_{13}H_{13}N_3 \cdot C_6H_3N_3O_7$: N, 19.09%).

Formation of 3a : To a solution of 2a (0.5 g) in ethanol (25.0 ml) phenyl isothiocyanate (0.5 ml) was added, and the mixture refluxed for 150 min. The solvent was then removed by distillation and 1-(N, N'-diphenyl) formamidino-3-phenylthiourea (3a) crystallised from ethanol (0.7 g), m.p. 165° (Found : N, 16.35 ; S, 9.05. Req'd. for $C_{20}H_{19}N_4S$: N, 6.18 ; S, 9.25%); ν_{max} 3 370 (NH), 1 550 (C=N) 1 370 (Ar) and 1 300 cm^{-1} (C-N); δ 6.69-6.93 (ArH).

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (M.U.A.) wishes to express thanks to Prof. K. N. Munshi for providing facilities and to the Ministry of Education, Government of India, for the award of a scholarship.

References

1. M. UMAR ALI and M. G. PARANJPE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, 62, 666.
2. M. UMAR ALI and M. G. PARANJPE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1984, 23, 573.
3. R. MOZINGO, *Org. Synth.*, 1965, 3, 181 ; 1941, 21, 15.
4. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 4th ed., Longmans, London, 1978, p. 736.
5. H. KRALL and R. D. GUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 629.
6. D. S. HECTOR, *Ber. Dtsch. Chem. Ges.*, 1889, 22, 1176 ; K. B. LAL and H. KRALL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 31 ; C. P. JOSHUA, V. K. VERMA and K. S. SURESH, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1961, 19, 663.
7. A. D. CROSS and R. A. JONLS, "An Introduction to Practical Infrared Spectroscopy", Plenum, New York, 1969.
8. R. M. SILVERSTEIN and G. C. BASSLER, "Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds", John Wiley, New York, 1963.
9. N. B. COLTHUP, L. H. DALY and S. B. WIBERLEY, "Introduction to Infrared and Raman Spectroscopy", Academic Press, New York, 1964.

Isolation of 16-Hentriacontanone, Alcohols and Sterols from the Leaves of *Annona squamosa*

MUKAT BEHARI* and RAJESH KUMAR SHARMA

Research Laboratories, S. V. College, Ahgarh-202 001

Manuscript received 17 May 1983, revised 14 November 1983, accepted 9 March 1984

THE leaves of *Annona squamosa* (Annonaceae) commonly known as Sarifah, are widely used as anthelmintic and also for other ailments¹. They contain an acrid principle fatal to insects² and used to kill lice³. The alcoholic extract of the leaves is reported to have anticancer⁴ activity. The survey of literature revealed that no other work, except the isolation of alkaloids^{4,5} and essential oils⁶ from the leaves has so far been carried out. The present note deals with the chemical examination of petroleum ether extractives of the leaves of this plant.

The air dried leaves of *A. squamosa* collected from the surroundings of Aligarh were extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°). The unsaponifiable fraction on column chromatography over silica gel was separated into three fractions.

Ketone : This fraction was obtained on elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) and purified with methanol as white amorphous powder, m.p. 83-84°; R_f 0.90 and ν_{max} 1 700 cm^{-1} (ketone). Gc-mass over OV-17 showed the single peak having molecular ion peak at m/e 450 and other peaks at m/e 254 and 239. It was identified 16-hentriacontanone on the above basis and by preparing its oxime, m.p. 57-58°.

Alcohols : This fraction was obtained on elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene (2 : 3) and purification from methanol as white solid, m.p. 85-86°; R_f 0.40 ; ν_{max} 1 070 and 3 200 cm^{-1} . Gc analysis over SE-30 represented it to be mixture of a homologous series of aliphatic alcohols with maximum participation of n-hexacosanol (C_{26} , 39%), n-octacosanol (C_{28} , 36%) and n-triacontanol (C_{30} , 19%) along with other homologues in small quantities. Even-carbon number alkanols⁷ were dominated.

Sterols : This fraction was obtained on further elution of the column with benzene and purified with methanol. It gave positive Liebermann-Burchard test and R_f 0.15. Its acetyl derivative was found to be a mixture of 24-methylcholest-5-ene-3 β -ol (campesterol), 24-ethylcholesta-5, 22-diene-3 β -ol (stigmasterol) and 24-ethylcholest-5-ene-3 β -ol (β -sitosterol) identified as acetate on the basis of co-argentation tlc. The major product, sitosteryl acetate was separated from the plate and was identified on the basis of co-tlc and m. m. p. The acetyl derivative on gc analysis over OV-17 confirmed the presence of campesterol (RRt=1.31, 28.6%), stigmasterol (RRt=1.42, 4.6%) and β -sitosterol (RRt=

1.62, 66.7%). R_{Rt} of sterol acetates were given relative to cholesterol.

The interesting observations reported earlier that alkanols⁸ possess anti-inflammatory activity comparable with β -methasone and β -sitosterol⁹ possesses anti-inflammatory activity, similar to hydrocortisone and oxyphenbutazone and antipyretic activity similar to acetyl salicylic acid, suggest that the presence of sterols and alkanols in the leaves of this plant might be responsible for its medicinal value.

Tlc (silica gel) plates were developed with carbon tetrachloride-ethyl acetate (95 : 5) for determining R_f values, whereas argentation tlc plates (silica gel-20% silver nitrate) were developed five times with methylene chloride-carbon tetrachloride (1 : 5, v/v) for separation of acetyl derivatives of sterols.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Dr. S. C. Gupta, Principal, S. V. College, Algarh, for providing facilities. Thanks are due to Prof. T. Matsumoto, Japan, for glc analysis, Dr. I. S. Ahuja for ir spectra and C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of Junior Research Fellowship to one of the authors (R.K.S.).

References

1. G. V. SATYAVATI, "Medicinal Plants of India", I.C.M.R., New Delhi, 1976, Vol. 1, pp. 75-76
2. R. N. CHOPRA, "Indigenous Drugs of India", Calcutta, 1958, p. 577.
3. K. R. KIRTIKAR and B. D. BASU, "Indian Medicinal Plants", Delhi, 1975, Vol. 1, p. 67
4. D. S. BHAKUNI, *Phytochemistry*, 1976, 18, 1584.
5. H. WANGE, M. REITER and W. FERSTL, *Planta Medica*, 1960, 40, 75.
6. R. N. CHOPRA, "Supplement of Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1974, p. 6.
7. M. BEHARI, C. K. ANDHIWAL and M. STREIBL, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1977, 42, 1385.
8. K. BASU, B. DASGUPTA, S. K. BHATTACHARYA, R. LAL and P. K. DAS, *Curr. Sci.*, 1971, 40, 86.
9. M. B. GUPTA, R. NATH, N. SHRIVASTAVA, K. SHANKER, K. KISHORE and K. P. BHARGAVA, *Planta Medica*, 1980, 39, 157.

Spectrophotometric Studies on Bisulphite-salicyldehyde Compound

S. P. CHATTOPADHYAY and ARABINDA K. DAS*

Department of Chemistry, University of Burdwan,
Burdwan-713 104

Manuscript received 12 September 1983, revised 28 June 1985, accepted 2 December 1985

THE addition compound between carbonyl group and bisulphite ion has an importance since it is a basis for the determination of many aldehydes and ketones¹. A series of aldehyde-bisulphite compounds have been studied and their dissociation

constants were determined by Keip and Bauer². Regarding spectrophotometric studies, a furfural-bisulphite complex have been described earlier³.

The present method may be used for the estimation of microgram quantities of bisulphite ion. The spectrophotometric studies can also be used to obtain quantitative information of aldehyde-sulphite equilibria.

Experimental

A 0.095 M stock solution of salicyldehyde (B.D.H., England) in ethanol-water (40%, v/v) was used. A 0.0034 M sulphite solution was prepared by dissolving reagent grade Na₂S₂O₃ (E. Merck, G.R.) in double-distilled water. All other chemicals used were reagent grade. All aqueous solutions were made by using double-distilled water.

Absorbance measurements were made on a Beckman 26 double beam uv-visible spectrophotometer equipped with 1 cm quartz cells. A Systonics 331 expanded scale pH meter equipped with glass electrode was used for pH measurements.

Procedure for the determination of sulphite: To an aliquot (0.5-2.0 ml) of the salicyldehyde solution (9.54×10^{-4} M) were added various amounts (0.5-6.0 ml) of a solution containing 50.0 to 550.0 μ g sulphite. pH of the solution was adjusted between 3.5 to 6.0 followed by addition of sodium dihydrogen phosphate buffer (1.0 ml). The volume of the resulting mixture was brought up to the mark in a 10 ml volumetric flask. The absorbance was measured at 256 nm after 30 min against the reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

Absorbance spectra: The absorbance value of salicyldehyde was found to decrease due to the formation of a complex with bisulphite ion. Fig. 1 shows typical absorption curves ($\lambda_{max} = 256$ nm) for salicyldehyde and bisulphite-salicyldehyde complex.

Working range: The absorbance values of several salicyldehyde solutions containing known amounts of sulphite were taken. In all cases, blanks were used as references. It was found that the absorbance values gradually decreased with the addition of sulphite. It is seen from Fig. 2 that such a decrease occurs linearly upto 55.0 ppm sulphite, and further addition of sulphite causes deviation from linearity. Thus, the working range for the determination of sulphite by using salicyldehyde has been found to be upto 55.0 ppm with the detection limit⁴ of 2.4 ppm.

Effect of pH and diverse ions: The absorbance values of solutions were sensitive to pH. Below pH 3.5, no appreciable⁴ absorbance difference between bisulphite ion and salicyldehyde was detectable. Above this pH, with the formation of higher amounts of bisulphite-salicyldehyde complex, the absorbance difference ($\bar{D}$) remained the same until